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Comparison of Dexmedetomidine or clonidine as adjuvant to Preemptive Thoracic Epidural Ropivacaine analgesia with propofol based TIVA in fast-track thoracic anaesthesia for open thoracic surgeries

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: -

Thoracic surgeries are very painful, I which require adequate anaesthesia& analgesia to modulate physiological responses of pain. In present study pre-emptive use of placebo/Dexmedetomidine / clonidine with Ropivacaine based perioperative thoracic epidural analgesia.

AIM & OBJECTIVES: -

To use both Alpha agonists with Ropivacaine for perioperative epidural analgesia with TIVA by propofol assessment of perioperative oxygenation, awareness, total dose of propofol, fast-tracking criteria were measured.

STUDY DESIGN:

A randomised retrospective observational study

METHODS:

In present study 75 adult patients of ASA grade, I/II of various elective thoracic surgeries in department of cardiothoracic & vascular surgery at V.S General hospital, NHLM Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS: -

Both Alpha agonists with Ropivacaine provide good RESULTS: - bolus propofol & fentanyl required to maintain BIS in comparison to Ropivacaine alone.

Fast-tracking criteria were comparable & good in each Group.

CONCLUSION-

Thoracic epidural analgesia with Ropivacaine definitely improved recovery, & provide good Fast-tracking criteria. Thoracic epidural Dexmedetomidine or clonidine with Ropivacaine provides better perioperative analgesia and improve Postoperative analgesia than Ropivacaine alone.

KEYWORDS: - Preemptive Thoracic epidural Ropivacaine, Dexmedetomidine, Clonidine, TIVA, One lung Anaesthesia, Open thoracic surgery.

Introduction

Surgical methods & anaesthetic techniques improved drastically over 2 decades. fast-tracking is new concept in surgical as well as anaesthesia field. Thoracic surgical stress causes impaired pulmonary function, pain, physiological delay which can impaired outcome of patients in form of prolonged postoperative ventilatory support, haemodynamic instability in form of arrhythmias. (2) To modulate these changes, we have given preemptive thoracic epidural analgesia to fast-track Anaesthesia outcome. (1)

Thoracic surgeries are very painful & pain induced changes in physiology causes intraoperative V/Q mismatch, delayed recovery, postoperative hypoxemia.

Thoracic epidural is gold standard for postoperative analgesia. This study particularly emphasises about preoperative improved oxygenation, & postoperative analgesia. (3)

Material & Methods:

In present Randomised controlled observational study after taking inform consent, we have enrolled 75 adult patients of ASA grade I/II of either gender undergoing open thoracic surgery. Randomisation was done by computerised Randomisation table, in sealed opaque envelopes. Execution of Randomisation at the time of giving anaesthesia.

Group Allocation:

Group RS (n=25) Inj. Ropivacaine 0.5% 8 ml in thoracic epidural catheter + Inj. NS 2 ml Group RD (n= 25) Inj. Ropivacaine 0.5% 8 ml + Inj. Dexmedetomidine 1 mcg/ kg in 2 ml NS Group RC (n=25) Inj. Ropivacaine 0.5% 8 ml + Inj. clonidine 1 mcg/kg in 2 ml NS.

Through Preoperative evaluation in form of General & systemic examination is done, baseline PFT, baseline ABGA were carried out the day before surgery.

In OT, after taking informed consent & preparing anaesthesia workstation for cardiopulmonary resuscitation, patient is taken in OT.

After securing 2 IV line with large bore canula, basic Monitors like Spo2, NIBP, ECG, were applied. Radial arterial line was secured under local anaesthesia.

With all aseptic & antiseptic precautions, preoperative epidural catheter was introduced in T5-6 or T6-7 space under local anaesthesia. Epidural space was located by loss of resistance technique. Epidural catheter was introduced upto 3-4 cm in space & fixed proper.

Thoracic epidural study drug was given according to group allocation.

General anaesthesia was given by inj. Thiopentone 2.5% IV 5-7 mg/ kg till loss of consciousness & inj succinylcholine 2 mg/kg. patients were intubated with appropriate size endobronchial tube, bilateral equal airtightness was checked. Isolation of tracheal & bronchial cuff was access clinically. proper suction was done from both tracheal & bronchial ports.

Maintenance was done by oxygen, inj vecuronium 0.1 mg/ kg, Inj propofol infusion of 6 mg/kg/hour. BIS was monitored throughout operation periodically, managed 40-60 by IV propofol & fentanyl aliquotes.

Epidural Top-up of study drug was repeated after 1 hour same as group allocation, as Ropivacaine is having intermediate duration of action.

Haemodynamic parameters were monitored every 5 min interval upto 30 min after induction, 10 min interval upto 1 hour, 15 minute interval in next hour, & finally 30 min interval till end of surgery.

Hypotension was defined as more than 20% decrease in SBP, which was treated by aliquotes of inj Ephedrine 3-6 mg.

Bradycardia was defined as more than 20% decrease in basal HR or <50/ min, it was treated with 0.6 mg inj. Atropine.

Perioperative awareness was assessed by **BIS**. If patients find mild awake, propofol bolus 20-30 mg was given or if tachycardia & hypertension (> 20% increase in basal SBP, & HR), were noticed, IV fentanyl 1 mcg/ kg was repeated with aliquotes of propofol 50 mg.

Arterial Blood Gas Analysis (ABGA) was assessed, baseline, after one lung position, at 15 min of isolation, 30 min of isolation to check oxygenation, V/Q mismatch.

IV fluids in form of crystalloids were given according to standard formula. Perioperative blood loss was corrected by Packed Cell Volume & colloids.

Heat loss was prevented by warm IV fluids temperature was maintained 35-36 degree.

Patients were reversed with inj glycopyrrolate & neostigmine after full fill of muscle reversal criteria.

Patients were watched for Fast-track criteria after extubation for recovery upto 6 hours postoperatively.

All patients were monitored in post-operative ICU periodically upto 24 hours regarding complications of surgery, epidural catheter related complications.

Postoperative VAS at rest & at coughing was measure periodically upto postoperative 6 hours. when VAS at rest was >3, rescue analgesia was given by epidural Tramadol 50 mg. Number of analgesic requests in 24 hours are noted in each group

(Epidural catheter was removed after 24 hours aseptically & blue tip was shown to patient & relatives for medicolegal purposes.)

FASTRACK CRITERIA: fast-tracking criteria was measured postoperatively, in following manner.

Level of consciousness

- Awake & orientation. 2
- Arousable with minimum stimulation 1
- Response only for tactile stimulation 0

Physical activity

- Able to move all extremities on command. 2.
- Some weakness in movement of extremities. 1
- unable to voluntarily move extremities. 0

Haemodynamic stability

- Decrease of 15% of baseline MAP. 2
- Change of 15%-30% of baseline MAP. 1
- Increase 30%of baseline MAP. 0

Respiratory stability

- Able to breathe deeply. 2 -Tachypnea with good cough. 1
- Dyspneic with weak cough. 0

Oxygen saturation

- Maintain value > 90% on room air. 2
- Requires supplemental oxygen to maintain oxygen saturation >90%. 1
- Saturation <90% with supplemental Oxygen. 0

Postoperative pain management

- None or mild discomfort. 2
- Moderate or severe pain control with IV analgesic. 1
- Persistent severe pain. 0

Postoperative emesis

- None or mild nausea with no active Vomiting. 2
- Transient vomiting controlled by IV antiemetic. 1
- Persistent moderate to severe vomiting 0

All patients were watched for early & late **complications** of surgery & anaesthesia.

Mean hospital stay (in days) was noted in each group.

Patient were followed up 15 days & 1 months postoperative for **pulmonary function tests, Xray chest, access for delayed complications.**

Statistical analysis:

All data were collected in Microsoft Excel spreadsheet.

All the data were analysed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) by SPSS Software IBM Armonk NY USA 2017.

Categorical variables were analysed by chi square test.

P < 0.05 was statistically significant. (S)

P < 0.001 was statistically highly significant. (HS)

P > 0.05 was statistically non-significant. (NS) **Observations and Results:**

Table 1**Demographics:**

Demographics parameters	Group RS	Group RD	Group RC	P value	Inference
Age in yrs.	45+/-3.8	46+/-2.6	47+/-2.4	>0.05	NS
Male/ female	12/13	13/12	14/11	-	-
Weight	55+/-3.6	58+/-3.2	55+/-2.8	>0.05	NS
BMI	27.05+/-3.02	28.04+/-3.31	28.32+/- 2.08	>0.05	NS
Pneumonectomy	13	14	12	>0.05	NS
Lobectomy	12	11	13	>0.05	NS
Duration of surgery(mins)	120.38+/-30.28	124.34+/-34.58	118.32+/-42.38	>0.05	NS

Demographics parameters were comparable for all 3 groups. (p > 0.05)

Table 2:

Total Dose of Rescue IV propofol & fentanyl required to maintain BIS

Parameters	Gr.RS	Gr. RD	Gr.RC	Pvalue	Inference
Total IV propofol (mg)	400+/-50	350+/-25	300+/-25	<0.001	HS

Total IV fentanyl (mcg)	200+/-25	150+/-25	150+/-25	<0.05	S
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Table 2 shows bolus of propofol required for maintenance was more in RS group. ($p < 0.05$) **Table 3:**

Perioperative BIS

Parameter	Group RS	Group RD	Group RC	Pvalue	Inference
BIS	40+/-10	39+/-12	37+/-13	>0.05	NS

Table 3 shows that BIS was successfully managed between 40-60 in all groups by bolus of IV propofol & fentanyl.

Postoperative analgesia:

Postoperative analgesia was given through epidural catheter in form of Tramadol 50 mg aliquotes when VAS at rest >3. No. of aliquotes were noted. inj. Diclofenac 75 mg was used as rescue analgesic. **Table 4**

Parameters	Group RS	Group RD	Group RC	P value	Inference
No. of analgesic requests(no.)	5+/-1	3+/-1.0	4+/-1	<0.05	S
Total Tramadol In mg	250+/-50	150+/-25	200+/-50	<0.001	HS

Table 5

Fast-tracking criteria

Fast-track criteria after extubation	Group RS	Group RD	Group RC	P value	Inference
At 15 min	9.8+/-2.8	10.8+/-2.3	10.4+/-2.2	>0.05	NS
At 30 min	10.2+/-1.5	11.2+/-1.8	11.0+/-1.4	>0.05	NS
At 1 hr	10.6+/-1.4	11.4+/-1.6	11.0+/-1.6	>0.05	NS
At 2 hr	11.6+/-1.2	12.1+/-1.8	12.0+/-1.4	>0.05	NS
At 4 hr	12.2+/-1.4	12.8+/-1.2	12.4+/-1.0	>0.05	NS
At 6 hr	12.4+/-1.6	12.9+/-1.1	12.5+/-1.2	>0.05	NS

Table 5 shows comparable fast-tracking criteria in all groups It suggests that preemptive thoracic epidural analgesia is gold standard for fast-tracking anaesthesia.

Table 6

Postoperative VAS at rest

VAS	Gr.RS	Gr RD	Gr..RC	P value	Inference
1 hour	2.33+/-1.4	1.90+/-1.2	2.1+/-1.0	>0.05	NS
2 hours	1.98+/-1.9	1.40+/-0.8	1.62+/-0.7	>0.05	NS
4 hours	1.88+/-1.2	1.2+/-0.7	1.4+/-0.4	>0.05	NS
6 hours	1.87+/-1.1	1.05+/-1.7	1.33+/-0.6	>0.05	NS
12 hours	1.92+/-0.9	1.5+/-0.8	1.72+/-0.4	>0.05	NS
24 hours	2.8+/-0.6	2.3+/-0.8	2.4+/-0.5	>0.05	NS

Table 7

VAS at coughing

VAS	Gr.RS	Gr. RD	Gr.RC	P value	Inference
1 hour	3.82+/-0.5	3.16+/-1.0	3.12+/-1.2	>0.05	NS
2 hours	2.9+/-1.2	2.5+/-1.1	2.6+/-1.4	>0.05	NS
4 hours	2.5+/-0.9	2.2+/-0.9	2.3+/-0.7	>0.05	NS
6 hours	2.4+/-1.1	2.1+/-1.3	2.2+/-1.2	>0.05	NS
12 hours	2.5+/-1.2	2.2+/-1.4	2.4+/-1.1	>0.05	NS
24 hours	2.2+/-1.4	1.9+/-0.5	1.8+/-0.9	>0.05	NS

No patient in any group has early **complications** like tachyarrhythmia, reexploration, late complications like Bronchopleural fistulas, etc.

Mean Hospital stay in each group was 5 -7 days which was comparable. ($p > 0.05$)

Patient were **followed up** 15 days & 1 months postoperatively for pulmonary function tests, PFT were normal & no delayed complications in any patient in each group.

Discussion:

Concept of fast-tracking is getting popular nowadays both in surgery & anaesthesia. It is successfully done in Cardiac, neuro, ambulatory onco, & various thoracic surgeries. (1)

Patients of open thoracic surgery like lobectomy & pneumonectomy are challenging for anaesthesia fast-tracking as we have to control physiological changes due to one lung ventilation, provide better haemodynamics, proper depth of anaesthesia, adequate analgesia as well as early recovery & extubation. (2)

Alpha 2 agonists Dexmedetomidine, Clonidine were approved by US FDA in 1999 for sedation, are now used for various Anaesthetic regimes & in various regional analgesic techniques as adjuvants. (11,12)

In present study we used TIVA with Propofol & TEA with study drugs for fast-tracking Thoracic anaesthesia.

Concept of preemptive analgesia is that providing analgesia to a patient before pain starts. Thoracic surgeries are more painful than abdominal surgeries. (2)

Bong et al (2) stated that effectiveness of preemptive epidural analgesia is clearer in thoracotomy surgeries than any other surgeries as thoracotomy provide noxious stimuli cause by central stimulation. (2)

Thoracic epidural analgesia is gold standard for open lung surgeries. During one lung ventilation there is some physiological V / Q mismatch. N₂O & Volatile agents uses for Maintenance of anaesthesia cause further derangement in this V/ Q mismatch. (2)

Yegin et al (3) also stated that preincisional Thoracic epidural is beneficial for outcome of thoracic surgery.

Amr et al exploration (4) carried out study, in which effects of preincisional epidural on pulmonary & endocrine system during one-lung ventilation, & shown that it provides better pulmonary function, oxygenation, Cortisol & Glucose levels found insignificant, as no effect on stress response.

Senturk et al (6) compared Thoracic Epidural Analgesia with or without preoperative initiation on postthoracotomy pain.

Perioperative BIS & ABGA were checked periodically & were within normal limits, & were **comparable**. (p>0.05)

VAS at rest & at coughing were checked in each group, In Ropivacaine group it was more but statistically Nonsignificant. (P>0.05)

Local Anaesthetic agent for thoracic epidural analgesia must have quick, long lasting analgesic effect, less motor effect, lower haemodynamic changes & high toxic dose limit, & wide margin of safety.

Ropivacaine is recent local anaesthetic agent which has better safety margin in comparison to Bupivacaine. (9)

Various studies prove that both Alpha 2 agonists Dexmedetomidine & Clonidine are good adjuvants to local anaesthetic agents. (11,12) we have taken 0.5% of Ropivacaine in all groups. as Yajun XU et al (9) stated that it provides better perioperative oxygenation. Yajun XU et al (9) also assessed thoracic epidural different concentrations of Ropivacaine, & effect on arterial oxygenation during one lung ventilation & concluded that TEA can be safe without problem in oxygenation during OLV. High concentrations of Ropivacaine 0.75% ,less propofol required. 0.5% Ropivacaine provide good analgesia, moderate propofol requirements, better perioperative oxygenation. (9)

Fast-tracking criteria in each group are good & comparable (P>0.05). In all groups we have given preemptive thoracic epidural analgesia so it provides better oxygenation, early extubation, prevent physiological derangement during one lung ventilation. (2,7).

Mean hospital stay was of less in open thoracic surgery as we have used preemptive thoracic epidural analgesia. Orchoch (7), Neustein SM et al also used preemptive thoracic epidural analgesia (TEA) & study its effect on longterm postoperative pain, pulmonary function, activity during recovery from major thoracotomy. They also summarise that preemptive thoracic epidural analgesia improve recovery. (7)

Prachi Kar (10) et al have given Epidural Dexmedetomidine during one lung ventilation & open thoracic surgery and improve oxygenation & decrease shunt fraction, perioperative anaesthetic & analgesic requirements.

Postoperative analgesic requests are more in RS group then in RD & RC group. (P<0.05)

Postoperative total rescue analgesia (Tramadol) was more in RS group, as Dexmedetomidine & Clonidine used in RD & RC group as adjuvant prolonged analgesic action of thoracic epidural Ropivacaine.

Conclusion:

In nutshell Thoracic epidural Ropivacaine with TIVA by Propofol provided Fast tracking anaesthesia in each group.

Both Alpha 2 agonists Clonidine & Dexmedetomidine are good adjuvants to Ropivacaine for preemptive Thoracic epidural analgesia which provides better postoperative analgesia without any complications.

Limitations:

we have given Thoracic Epidural Analgesia in each Group, there was no control group. we have not checked endobronchial tube by fiber-optic bronchoscopy.our sample size was of 75 total case; future large-scale study requires.

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Nil

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